

The Impact of Social Media on English Speaking and Writing Skills of Learners: A Study Conducted among the Students and Teachers of UAE Universities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 06, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: January 08, 2025</p> <p>Keywords : English Writing Skills, Speaking skill, EFL Teacher, EFL Students, Social Media</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14622764</p>	<p><i>Based on the immense importance of learning English as an international language and the issues that teachers face to motivate the students towards learning English as a foreign language. The current study is established to examine the importance of using social media platforms on EFL learners' writing and speaking skills. Therefore, the main objective of the study is to find out the extent to which social media helps students in improving their writing and speaking skills along with impact of social media on EFL learners' abilities to learn. Data was collected from EFL teachers (45) and EFL students (124) teaching and studying at Universities of United Arab Emirates. The results of the study revealed that social media significantly impact the EFL students' speaking and writing skills based on understanding that students respond positively in language classrooms when exposed to modern technology. Therefore, teachers must focus to enrich their teaching process by appropriately using social media for promoting a global understanding among the EFL learners for effectively interacting and communicating in English Language.</i></p>

Introduction

In recent years, English as an international language got substantial importance (Hosseini & Seifoori, 2019) but the process of learning has never been easy for students and teachers. During the learning process, students have to learn various skills varying from listening to speaking (Genc, 2016). Along with the students, teachers also have to face distinct issues that should be handled effectively. One of the main issues that teachers come across is how to motivate the students towards learning a foreign language. In addition, what makes the situation even more complicated is that some teachers are still using traditional techniques and methods (Saidouni, K., & Bahloul, 2018) which do not provide the required environment for students to learn speaking and writing comfortably.

To motivate the students towards learning a foreign language, teachers and instructors should use such methodologies that enhance the learner's interest in the new language (Alizadeh, 2016). It is understood that without using these strategies, students can't learn in class as many factors restrict their communicative competence (Kakar & Pathan, 2017). The student of the twenty first century can never learn how to speak and write by drills or words learned by heart, he would rather be motivated to learn if the learning itself is interesting and entertaining. In today's digital world, usage of social media is considered as a useful cultivating tool if used properly (Namaziandost et al., 2019).

There are many learners of English as a foreign language (Namaziandost & Ahmadi, 2019). Students are looking all the time to improve their writing and speaking skills because EFL is mainly taught in terms of grammar and structures. In past, there has been research in the area of speaking and writing English (Bravo et al., 2017; Novikova et al., 2018; Sabirova & Khanipova, 2019; Setiyadi et al., 2019; Sundari, 2017) but very less studies have focused upon both sides in a single study. As a matter of fact, the usage of social media during learning and teaching is of much importance to communicate with different people around the world. Starting from this point we need to know if Social Media have any effects on EFL learners' speaking and writing skills.

The current study wants to help the EFL learners that how they can perform well by improving their writing and speaking skills of English language. It is of great importance to explore that to which extent Social media can help education and EFL members (Dehghan et al., 2017; Reinhardt, 2019; Taskiran et al., 2018; Xodabande, 2017) especially with the inventions of new technologies. Concerning the main problem of the study, speaking and writing skills of English language is crucially paramount because it serves the purpose of communication. We believe that this study will open the door to new unprecedented approaches and pedagogies that will enrich the domain of teaching and learning in the EFL context in the future. This study is also of great importance because of English language which is most ubiquitous as people around the world use it to share their ideas and communicate.

Hence, this study is designed to find answer to main research question that is to what extent Social Media helps students in improving their writing and speaking skills?

Literature Review

Past research on EFL has observed an inordinate amount of changes in strategies, procedures, and sometimes roles of teachers and learners. Despite this, the goal has always been the same which is making EFL learners communicatively competent in the target language and shape their proficiency to meet the different challenges of life in real situations (Nasri et al., 2018). At present, EFL teaching and learning has been influenced by the technological innovation, and many tools have been added to the English class to facilitate the process of teaching/learning in order to provide a more genuine environment for learners to mention but a few of these tools one can cite: the Data show, computers, and recorded tapes. However, there should be a great need to update these tools as the time goes on, in order to keep up with the advancement of ICT's in the world.

The overwhelming usage of Social media among learners and even teachers proved itself as a successful tool to education. Similarly, most teachers believe that the idea behind learning a language is to be able to write and speak it fluently and accurately. So, it means that just understanding a language should not necessarily construct the assumption that a person have the knowledge of that specific language (Namaziandost et al., 2019; Nasri & Biria, 2017). The learner should accomplish a great level of proficiency in the four language skills including speaking and writing. However, to have a strong grip on foreign language is not an easy task, and it is definitely not as easy as speaking or writing a mother tongue. As a solution, according to past research, by apt use of social media teachers can make students learn the foreign language easy and bit stress-free.

Speaking Skill

In societal context, speaking skill is the basis of communication between people. It refers to "the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts" (Chaney, 1998, p. 13). Further, it was defined as a volatile process of being able to understand a language including sharing information (Brown, 1994; Burns & Joyce, 1997). All these perspectives see speaking as a whole side of learner's daily lives in receiving and producing speech. Speaking is an important language skill for learners and teachers. To have a grip upon a foreign language it is essential to be able to speak it in both teaching-learning process.

It has occupied a significant and delicate rank all the way through the history of language teaching. Despite its importance, teaching and learning has been undervalued but past 20 years saw the research in the area of teaching a foreign language (Hosseini et al., 2017). Speaking English language is not considered as only to be able to pronounce English words. Therefore, English teachers dedicate supreme time to speaking to smooth the augmentation of English learners' proficiency. The four skills are considered the key as far as language teaching is concerned i.e. speaking, writing, reading and listening.

Speaking, yet is a skill which deserves the attention of researchers that will help the students and teachers for the professional advancement and of business. Perhaps then, the teaching of speaking merits more thought.

Writing Skills

In communication among people, writing is considered as an important tool for sharing information with others. But in the context of EFL, learners start to write English words very lately as compared to their first language (Nalliveettil & Mahasneh, 2017). For EFL learners, it is difficult to write in English language that makes their writing proficiency level poor and thus they have to face difficulties in educational and professional life. It is challenging for both teachers and learners that how they can make this learning process a bit easier and interesting so, it becomes necessary for language teachers to take such steps through which they can guide their students in improving their writing skills.

All four skills of language are considered equally important for getting proficiency in EFL but in classroom, writing is used more than others as teachers use it to assess the performance level of students (Mohammad & Hazarika, 2016). An EFL learner can't acquire writing skills naturally as it needs a lot of effort to learn the word, their meanings, structure of sentences etc. Thus, it is important for learners that they should know how they can have effective writing skills in EFL.

The language teachers utilize various writing activities such as paragraph writing, taking notes, writing tests etc. to improve their writing skills. To get the better writing skills of students, EFL language teachers adopt some strategies to make the process of EFL teaching-learning more fruitful (Nalliveettil & Mahasneh, 2017). But past research has given very less attention to the writing skills in learning English language (Marzban & Jalali, 2017).

Issues in the class of English as a foreign language

It is necessary for a language teacher to make his students learn the English language effectively, so they focus on difficulties faced by learners to learn oral expression. It is because the current oral production class is teacher centered, despite the various attempts teachers make to engage learners in discussions and motivate them to learn, the amount of speeches students have are still not sufficient. Besides, the Spoken language toward that students are attentive does not facilitate the communicative competencies imperative in real life situations. It is understood that in today's world having proficiency in English language leads the student towards success in educational and professional life (Baker & Westrup, 2003).

In the same line of thought, speaking and writing is considered tough similarly in reference to the English language class because students' focus is not just upon the learning as they also have to learn to engage with each other in social context. In addition to what has been mentioned earlier, many other factors prevent learners from reaching oral expression proficiency in class most of which are psychological, for instance, anxiety and inhibition. Various methods can be adopted by teachers to motivate the students towards learning a foreign language (Namaziandost, et al., 2019), one of the main strategies is using social media to improve the students' writing and speaking skills.

Usage of technology in EFL Classroom

Past research has observed the rapid expansion of the usage of technology in learning English as a foreign language classroom. Internet largely reduced the distances between people, saved time and made things easier. There is need to use such technology that facilitate the teachers in teaching EFL. Thus, usage of technology in education is necessary for students and teachers both to meet learning challenges (Aziz et al., 2013). Now a days, using traditional methods in classroom by a teacher produces obstacles for students in learning process. Consequently, students of a teacher who introduces and uses the technology in classroom are the quick learner as compared to others as it reduces the ambiguity and anxiety level of students and facilitate them in whole learning process (Akinola, 2015; Haigh, 2010; Levy, 2009; Namaziandost & Shafiee, 2018; Pichette, 2009).

Social media

The term 'social media' is derived from 'social networks' in which the word 'social' refers to connection among people while the networks is the extent to which different computer systems are linked with each other (Eren, 2012; Namaziandost et al., 2018). Social media is refers to the communication through web and cellular phones. As for now technology has the prominent importance in education that helps the students and teachers in learning process especially EFL. Social media as a learning tool has noticeably of greater use among teachers and learners in EFL. This usage has attracted researchers towards exploring the usage of social media and its effectiveness in the classroom for both teachers and learners (Hashemifardnia et al., 2018; Paliktzoglou & Suhonen, 2014).

In recent years, educational institution has made the presence of social media in classroom activities as an important tool some of which are Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, blogs etc. So, these institutions have facilitated their students and teachers in learning English as a second language. This usage of social media takes the mentality of learning a foreign language beyond traditional methods. By keeping in mind so much importance of social media in learning process, and the hurdles faced by students in pure traditional learning method, there is need to focus upon the consideration of these methods that entertain and motivate students learning English as a foreign language.

The usage of social media as a learning tool improves the learning process including speaking and writing skills by enhancing their interest make them enthusiastic towards learning (Gibbins & Greenhow, 2016; Hashemifardnia et al., 2018). As in modern times, social media have entered in people's lives, it is tremendously important to analyze its effectiveness.

To sum up, it is worth stating that speaking and writing EFL is not an easy task to teach so, teachers should be aware of their students' needs and requirements in order to achieve proficiency. EFL teachers are also inclined to give ICTs their fair share of importance and utility in class. Teachers on their part should make use of technologies as accurately as possible for their students and themselves. It is indeed the ultimate way to keep the strategies up to date. ICTs nowadays are imposing themselves as a necessity in EFL classroom.

METHOD

The

population

Current study is established on survey methodology involving both English as a Foreign Language teachers (N=45) and students (N=124) at Universities of UAE. Two Google survey were prepared. One was sent to teachers and other to students. The research was conducted among the teachers and students of teaching and learning English as a foreign language. The EFL teachers and student were selected for survey during the academic year 2020/2021. Survey questions consisted of two parts. Part 1 containing all the information regarding demographic features of the respondents whereas, in part 2 different questions were included regarding use of social media by the teachers and students and the impact of social media on EFL learners English language speaking and writing skills. As the teachers play an imperative role in in the enhancement of

language learning skills of the students. In addition, teachers when involved in oral discussion with learners using different social media platforms it automatically enhances the language learning skills of the EFL learners. Total 75 teachers were approached, and questionnaire was sent top them via email and other social media networks but we received complete data set of 45 respondents only. Students were basically chosen based on their participation in different social media groups created by the learners for study purpose. Students usually share study material in these groups or communicate with their teachers via these groups. In total 2500 students were approached but we received 124 questionnaires back.

Research

As the research instrument is considered to be the backbone of any survey study (Dornyei & Ushioda, 2011) therefore, we used two questioners adopted from the Namaziandost & Nasri, (2019). Basically the same questions were asked from the teachers and students with a slight difference in the style .

Instruments

RESULTS

Analysis of Teachers' Questionnaire

The questionnaire was addressed to 45 EFL teachers. This questionnaire was basically developed to have some idea about the use of social media among the EFL teachers and learner. This questionnaire consists of seven questions. The detailed analysis is as follows.

Question 1. How often do you use Social media?

Question 2. Have you ever used Social media for educational purposes?

Figure 1: Teachers' answers to the questions related to intensity of use of social media and their use for educational purpose

In a question related to the intensity of use of social media as shown in figure 1, respondents were asked that how often they use social media. Their answer was based on 5-point likers scale ranging from frequently to never. In response to this question 71.4% respondents stated that they always use social media whereas in contrast 14.3% respondents stated that they rarely use social media. The second question was specifically related to use of social media for educational purpose. The respondents had to give answer either in yes or no. The main aim behind this question was to discover how teachers use Social media to achieve any educational goals. In response to this question all of them replied yes. This shows that all the teachers who participated in survey use social media for teaching purpose in one or the other way such as sharing lectures, publishing useful links or sending messages to colleagues or students, while only one teacher used Social media to give lectures. It also implies that those teachers who rarely use social media for other purposes also use social media for educational purposes. This reflects the importance of social media in teaching activities.

Question 3. How much do you get in touch with learners through the use of Social media?

Question 4. Among the different types of social media, there are social media that are mostly based on oral communication ... which one is your favorite?

Figure 2: Teachers' answers to the questions related their interaction with learners through social media and choice of social media platform

Regarding the third question, the rationale of this question was to figure out if teachers benefit from Social media at the level of communicating information and ideas with EFL learners. In response to this question related to the interaction of the teachers with students on social media (figure 2) 71.4% of the teachers replied that they frequently get in touch with their students through social media whereas, 14.3% responses revealed that they are not very active in interacting with students on social media as they selected rarely in their response. In question four, knowing about which Social media teachers prefer was the ultimate goal of the question.

Teachers and even learners may have different Social media to use when they seek oral communication therefore, it was very important to our research to know which Social media ranks the best among EFL teachers. In response to this question 57% teachers selected zoom, 28.6% teachers selected WhatsApp and 14.3% selected Skype. Whereas, responses revealed that none of the respondents use telegram or Google teams for communicating educational materials or activities with their students. This reflect that in UAE most common social media platforms for educational purposes are zoom, WhatsApp and Skype.

Question 5. Which language is mostly used when using these tools?

Question 6. To what extent can Skype, zoom, Google teams, WhatsApp and Telegram be helpful to students? and why?

Figure 3: Teachers' answers to the questions related to use of language and helpfulness of social media platforms in educational activities

Question five was administered in an attempt to know which language is being used by teachers when using Social media and also to see if teachers are making use of these Social media to contribute to the whole field of education. The result denotes the remarkable control of English over the other languages in use, research shows that most teachers (75.2%) use English as the main Language in oral communication, whereas, 24.6% use Arabic. Question six was regarding the helpfulness of the social media platforms in education activities and learning English as a foreign language. In response to this question majority of the teachers (71.4%) represented the high impact of social media to facilitate the students in educational activities like the level of language practice in terms of speaking and writing whereas, 28.6% reported the medium level usefulness of social media platforms to achieve educational goals of the studies. And surprisingly no one selected the low importance of social media platforms in terms of educational effectiveness.

Question 7. Why Skype, zoom, Google teams, WhatsApp and Telegram be helpful to students?

Figure 4. Teachers' answers to the questions related to reasons of using social media platforms

Finally, question seven was designed in an attempt to know the teachers' point of view about the main issue of the whole research which is the influence of Social media on the students speaking and writing skill; it also includes an opportunity for teachers to justify their opinions. Accordingly, the results display that the overall number of teachers believe that social media do have an impact on the students' level of language practice in terms of speaking and writing. As the results show, that 17.6% teachers stated that social media platforms are helpful for the students because they practice the language and 76.4% stated that social media acts a motivational factor for the students to speak and write English in their conversations and 8.6% teachers were of the view that students need face to face interactions while studying that's why social media platforms are preferred to be used.

Analysis of the Students' Questionnaire

This questionnaire was mainly designed for students. A total number of 124 students answered this questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of six questions results are as follows.

Question 1. How often do you use Social media?

Question 2. Have you ever used Social media for educational purposes?

Figure 1. Students' answers to the questions related to intensity of use of social media and their use for educational purpose

The first question was asked for two main reasons the first was to engage the participant in the topic so that he/she constructs a previous knowledge about what is coming next of questions. Secondly, to know how far students are attached to Social media. 39.5% participants stated that they frequently use Social media, while 11.3% students reported a regular use of social media on the other hand 33 participants were neutral about their answer and 11 reported rarely use of social media reflecting that for them social media is not a priority and therefore, they use the social media platforms only sometimes. Regarding the second question, it was very important for the researcher to know the students' standpoint about the influence of Social media simply because they represent an effective part in the phenomenon. The results have shown that most students (92.7 %) use social media platforms for study purpose and only 8.1% of the respondents denied their use of social media for study purpose.

Question 3. How much do you get in touch with learners through the use of Social media?

Question 4. Among the different types of social media, there are social media that are mostly based on oral communication ... which one is your favorite?

Figure 6. Students' answers to the questions related their interaction with learners through social media and choice of social media platform

The findings of the third question revealed the mixed as 21% and 22% students stated that they get in touch with their teachers frequently and most of the time. Where 40.3% did not reflected anything, they gave a neutral response and 3 students said they never get in touch with their teachers via social media platforms. The fourth question was addressed to EFL students to know which Social media is mostly used or favored by students. The answers concerning this question have revealed that WhatsApp is the most favored Social media between students making up 52.4% of users, while Zoom occupied the second most used social media with up 29.8% responses. Telegram on the other hand ranked the third with 8 users. Whereas, only 1 reported the use of Skype. These results were quite different than the teacher's responses.

Question 5. Which language is mostly used when using these tools?

Question 6. To what extent can Skype, zoom, Google teams, WhatsApp and Telegram be helpful to students? and why?

Figure 7. students' answers to the questions related to use of language and helpfulness of social media platforms in educational activities

Question five was devised to determine the language that students mostly use when using Social media. This question was very essential to the research work. It shows its significance as far as English language is concerned. The research has displayed that 62.9% use English as the main language for oral communication in Social media while the others opt for the Arabic. Some students opted for more than one choice which means that they shift from one language to the other according to the speakers' need. Behind question five, the researcher

aimed to know the extent to which students of English are making use of Social media as the researcher wanted to know EFL students' attitudes and ideas towards the employment of Social media in educational fields to improve speaking skill. The majority of students 56.4% think that Social media improve the speaking proficiency to a high extent, while 45.2% of students claimed that the medium level of improvement and only 4 students reported the low level of social media effect in improvement of their speaking and writing skills .

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

First of all, it is worth saying that teachers at the university are conscious of the advancement and progress of communication and technology and its assumption to the field of education, and teachers play an imperative role in it by publishing educational links and sharing knowledge with their students using social media platforms. Moreover, the benefit gained from Social media is dependent, and differs from one teacher to another, in the same vain only few teachers use Social media for online lecturing. In addition, Zoom, WhatsApp and Skype have got quite large popularity among teachers in comparison with other Social media. Thus, their use involves mostly colleagues and not students. Furthermore, teachers believe in the influence of Social media helping their standpoint with the fact that Social media give the students the opportunity to practice the language due to the motivating and helpful environment it provides. In addition. teachers regard "Virtual Classroom" as a very successful experience and would enhance the student writing and speaking abilities through the conversations conducted with native speakers of English. Similarly, teachers do agree that Social media can be used at university to improve speaking and writing as well. The main challenge, however, lies at the pedagogic strategies that should be followed in order to implement Social media and how they can best be employed, not to mention the availability of necessary equipment.

On the other hand, social media has become a daily habit among students and the integration of online conversations in English class should provide an atmosphere of enjoyment as well as facilitate them to improve their writing and speaking skills. Students use different social media platforms for various purposes ranging from education to communication and entertainment. Among the students most popular media are WhatsApp and Skype and this makes a lot of sense because on WhatsApp the communication is easy and quick and considered to be an additional tool and connected to the most used Social media all over the world. The research has revealed that English is the most used language among students when using Social media with a challenging degree of use of mother tongue as well and maybe that is exactly the reason why the improvement is seen with "Virtual Classroom" students and not with other students. As students are encouraged and guided to communicate only in English in the Virtual Classroom. In a question designed for students about the use of Social media to improve speaking most students welcomed the thought and claimed its effectiveness in learning and improving speaking and writing skills. Our study has been focused on the effectiveness of the use of Social media to improve EFL learners speaking and writing skill. An analysis was performed in order to confirm the results that have been obtained from both students and teachers' questionnaire. The findings went hand in hand with our hypothesis which emphasize that learners will enhance their speaking skill if they use Social media in an appropriate way.

The aim of this study was to investigate if there are any positive effects or influence of Social media on EFL learners speaking and writing skill and determine to what extent Social media can be an assistant for the teachers to improve their application of speaking and writing activities in order to encourage their learners to participate and improve their speaking and writing skill, because the majority of students want to use these aids in the classroom continuously in order to avoid the bored study and make them motivated to participate in speaking activities. Above all, it is worth explaining that Social media cannot be regarded only as an entertaining tool, they rather play a principal role in the field of education and research, the presence of Social media has changed some of the aspects in the teacher and the learner roles towards clarity and flexibility and therefore, instructors may be looking forward to implement different pedagogies so as to keep up with the technological advancements.

Recommendations

As the technology might be a convenient means to fulfill the goals of improving speaking and writing skills of the EFL learners. The general findings of the current study revealed that the use of Social media is becoming broader and broader among learners as well as teachers. They both make use of it in different fields to achieve different goals including educational ones. Besides the fact that Social media provide time and shorten the distances, they create a relaxing context for learners to talk freely and express their ideas without any fear of embarrassment or lack of confidence. Therefore, they help the learners to overcome many speaking difficulties and boost their speaking skill. After the analysis of the findings obtained students and teachers' questionnaires, we suggest the following recommendations:

For teachers:

- Teachers are advised to use Social media in preparing classroom speaking activities.
- Teachers should encourage their students to be exposed to authentic language through Social media.
- Teachers should exploit videos from Social media in their courses in order to enhance learners' motivation to speak.

For students

- Students should use Social media appropriately in order to develop their speaking and writing skill.
- Students should communicate with native speakers in order to develop their speaking skill.
- Students should be interested in study material because they will help them in learning English language with new technology.
- Students should benefit from watching Social media' video courses and using various Social media.

For Administration

- The administration should provide the necessary materials that are required to promote the speaking ability.
- The administration should provide the necessary materials that are required to facilitate learners to enhance their writing skills.
- Social media should be considered as a strategy in teaching the oral and written courses.

Finally, it is evident that due to its enormous application in our routine life social media play an imperative rule in our learning activities. Therefore, teachers must apply the flexible strategies as per the requirement of the students and provide as much as space for the students to express their ideas and develop their oral competence so that they can learn the EFL at their best capacity. The integration of Social media in EFL context will provide access to increase the language activities and even more, to enhance the student's motivation to learn speaking and writing which is believed to be the main factor that lacks the traditional classroom. Without a shadow of doubt, the frequent communication with native speakers around the world by means of Social media would improve the student speaking skills. Therefore, it became a necessity to give technology its fair share of importance in EFL context.

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